

Moderating Effect of Age and Gender on the Relationship Between Electronic Word of Mouth and Fast-food E-reputation in Togo

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Abstract:

The concept of e-reputation is the result of the rapid technological development of the Internet and its use by individuals and businesses. The emergence of Web 2.0 has led to a growing awareness of the importance of digital reputation or e-reputation and its vital role in ensuring the smooth running, success and longevity of a company. The aim of this study is to verify the moderating effect of gender and age on the relationship between electronic word of mouth and the e-reputation of fast-food restaurants in Togo. To do this, a survey was conducted among a sample of 374 Internet users. The results show that this relationship evolves in the same way for men and women, regardless of age.

Key words: Electronic word of mouth; e-reputation

1- Introduction

The emergence of the Internet has provided consumers with tools enabling them to communicate with each other and exchange information about companies, their brands and their products. This is known as 'electronic word of mouth' (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004). This information becomes a privileged means for Internet users to forge an image that is less framed and less oriented than that conveyed by official brand sites 'le-reputation' (Céline FUEYO, 2015). Consumers find themselves at the centre of an infinite system of exchange in which opinions, ideas and criticisms are constantly circulating. Furthermore, the literature has shown that socio-demographic variables (age, gender, etc.) play an important role in consumer behaviour and, in particular, in individuals' reactions to communicative stimuli. (Manceau & Tissier-Desbordes, 1999). However, in the context of electronic BAO communication, few studies have examined the role that these socio-demographic variables might play in the reactions of consumers exposed to E-BAO. In this context, Cheung and Thadani (2012) recommend further studies to better understand the impact of socio-demographic variables on E-BAO exposure. (Ben Jeddou, 2019) investigated the influence of electronic word-of-mouth on e-reputation, but using only one variable (the moderating role of source credibility). In his limitations and perspectives, he recommends broadening the scope by using other variables socio-demographic variables. This is what mainly motivated us to conduct this research, and we were interested in studying the impact of two socio-demographic variables, age and gender, on e-reputation in the context of electronic word-of-mouth on fast food in Togo. To our knowledge, no study has yet looked at the impact of gender and age variables on e-reputation following exposure to electronic word-of-mouth and especially in the context of fast food in Togo; and given that a number of previous studies have already shown the moderating role of these variables on consumer behaviour in general, we decided to look at the influence of these variables in the context of electronic word-of-mouth on the e-reputation of fast food in Togo. The aim of our research is therefore to examine the possibility of a difference in response between men and women and between age groups after exposure to electronic BAO. Specifically, we seek to answer the following question: To what extent can the gender and age of the recipient have a moderating effect between exposure to an e-BAO and e-reputation?

This research is structured in four parts. We begin with a literature review highlighting the main roles of age and gender in consumer behaviour and exposure to online OBA. This literature will serve as a basis for formulating hypotheses and a conceptual model for our research. Next, we present our research methodology. This will be followed by the main results obtained and a discussion of these results. Finally, we will conclude by outlining the main contributions of our study, its shortcomings and avenues for future research.

2- Theoretical framework

2.1. Electronic word-of-mouth

With the proliferation of the Internet and the widespread use of NICTs, consumers have been given a very powerful tool for seeking information and sharing experiences with other consumers on the web, namely electronic word-of-mouth. Electronic word of mouth does not have a fixed definition. There are several definitions, depending on the author. The following table presents the main definitions used in the literature review and their authors. Heinnig-Thurau et al (2004) define electronic word of mouth as any positive or negative information given by former, current or potential consumers about a product or company via the Internet. According to Godes and Mayzlin (2004), electronic word-of-mouth is a particular form of classic word-of-mouth. Unlike traditional word-of-mouth, which is limited to a local social network, the impact of online reviews and comments can go beyond a local community to reach people anywhere in the world, as any consumer seeking information can access a website, regardless of their location.

2.2. E-reputation

E-reputation is the idea, the opinion, the view that people have of an entity (individual, company, brand, etc.) based on its digital identity, i.e. the traces it has left voluntarily or involuntarily online.

Frochot and Molinaro (2008, p. 13) state that e-reputation ‘also known as cyber reputation, digital reputation or web reputation is the image that Internet users form of a company or a person based on the information disseminated about them on the Web, what others say about them, messages disseminated by various Internet users (customers, competitors, employees, etc.) or traces left involuntarily’. According to Origgi (2007), e-reputation is Internet-based reputation. It raises the issue of reputation management through messages exchanged freely on the Internet, which are largely beyond the control of corporate communication departments. This raises the question of how to control the messages conveyed via the internet and the buzz (word-of-mouth) that has become a very important and effective communication channel (Keller, 2007). "E-reputation affects more people [than reputation], because of the accessibility of information (Castellano and Dutot 2013, p. 30). What's more, this information lasts over time because of the history of the written word. Control of the message no longer lies entirely within

the company, but also with the stakeholders who can, even unwittingly, have a major influence on the company's reputation.

2.3. The moderating role of gender

In the context of e-reputation, studies of consumer behaviour have clearly shown that gender can influence consumer reactions. This research shows that men and women react differently to websites, the design of online information and navigation (Cyr & Bonanni, 2005). For example, Garbarino, E., & Strahilevitz, M. (2004), put forward the idea that women seem less interested in the Internet since they tend to spend less time online than men. They suggest that women are generally less sensitive to online shopping than men. Indeed, it appears that women are more likely than men to use word of mouth from a variety of sources (Walker, 1995).

Furthermore, in research conducted by Bae, S., & Lee, T. (2011), which focused on online comments, the results showed that the effects of online comments on e-reputation were greater for women than for men.

It is therefore possible to put forward the following hypothesis:

H1. The gender of the consumer has a moderating effect on the electronic BAO relationship and e-reputation

2.2 The moderating role of age

The marketing literature has already shown that age differences between individuals can have an impact on attitudes and behaviour (Klippel and Sweeney, 1974; Beatty and Smith, 1987). For example, compared with younger subjects, older people show greater reluctance to adopt new technologies (Gilly & Zeithaml, 1985), become more cautious, and seek greater certainty in their decision-making. More specifically, age seems to play an important role in information processing. Research has shown that young and old people process information differently and expose themselves to information differently. It should be noted that this age difference also comes into play when selecting sources of personal and informational information (Shanas, 1968).

Hence the following hypothesis:

H2. Consumer age has a moderating effect on the electronic BAO relationship and e-reputation

Summary table of hypotheses

Based on hypotheses H1 and H2, we can therefore assume that gender and age represent two moderating variables that can have an impact on the relationship between exposure to electronic OBA and corporate e-reputation. This relationship is represented schematically in the conceptual model.

Figure1: Conceptual Model

Conceptual Model

This model shows both direct and indirect links between the different variables. In other words, gender and age are considered as moderating variables between the other variables in this model. Furthermore, the aim is to highlight the existence or otherwise of the moderating effect of gender and age between electronic word-of-mouth and e-reputation.

3- Methodology

Our research is part of a hypothetico-deductive approach which consists of following a linear and invariant process aimed at translating theoretical analyses into research hypotheses which are then tested in the field through empirical situations considered to be representative (Si et al., 1976). In the first part, we presented the research stages of the first phase in relation to the formulation of research questionnaires. Our aim is to conduct an empirical study based on a questionnaire survey in order to test the proposed research framework. A pre-test will be carried out to ensure the suitability and validation of the measurement scales. A final survey will then be carried out to verify the proposed research hypotheses.

3.1- Sample selection and data collection

For the purposes of this study, non-probabilistic methods appear to be the most appropriate for our study, since we do not have a sampling frame specific to our target population, so we can determine the sample size using a given statistical formula. The most suitable non-probabilistic method is the convenience sample, as it is easy to find students or parents to interview. As a result, we were able to reach three hundred and sixty-eight (450) respondents, and after processing the data, we were left with three hundred (374) respondents. Our quantitative data were collected online and in Togolese fast food outlets. The method chosen for collecting quantitative data was a questionnaire survey and online data collection. These methods make it possible to collect a certain amount of anonymous and confidential data from a representative sample of the target population, and to give respondents a certain amount of freedom to give their opinions on the subject. It should be noted that before launching the actual data collection, a pre-test of our data collection instrument was carried out.

3.2- Operationalisation of variables

the variables taken into account in this research are:

- Dependent variable (E-REPUTATION)
- Independent variable (E-BAO)
- Moderating variables (Gender and Age)

The Likert interval scale was used to measure these different variables. It has the advantage of categorising, arranging and organising the items, and enables the differences between the different levels of the scale to be assessed.

The five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 to 5: 'strongly disagree', 'somewhat disagree', 'no opinion', 'somewhat agree', and 'strongly agree', is preferred to the three- or seven-point scale for measuring the different variables in our study for the following reasons: First of all, our study takes into account two categories of individuals: students and parents. We will have online respondents who can answer from anywhere. This choice is also justified by the reasons given by (Sogbossi Bocco, 2010) on the managers of small businesses in Africa, where those surveyed were unable to distinguish between expressions such as: 'very good' and 'good', 'bad' and 'mediocre' (Sogbossi, 2012). The confusion generally observed with these expressions makes the seven-point scale inoperative. This means that the five-point Likert scale should be used for surveys in underdeveloped countries.

3.3-Items

In order to focus our research, we do not aim to develop a new measurement scale for the concepts of our research, but we will use existing measurement scales in the literature that have been developed and tested in the Togolese context. The choice of measurement scales will be justified in three groups in the next headings: scales of independent variables, scales of dependent variables and scales of moderating variables.

Our conceptual model includes two dependent variables: e-Bao and e-reputation, and two moderating variables: gender and age. In the rest of our work, we will present the scales used for each of these variables

Word of mouth scale (Bambauer-Sachse & Mangold, 2011)

BAO1: I often read other customers' online reviews of fast-food restaurants to find out which fast food restaurants have a good impression of them.

BAO2: To make sure I choose the right fast food, I often read customer reviews online

BAO3: I often consult other online customers' reviews of fast-food restaurants to help me choose my establishment

BAO4: I frequently gather information about fast food from online customer reviews before choosing my establishment

BAO5: If I don't read online reviews of a fast-food restaurant I worry about my decision

BAO6: When I choose a fast-food restaurant, online customer reviews give me the confidence to book it.

To measure electronic word-of-mouth, we opted for the Bamauer-Sachse & Mangold scale (2011). It consists of 6 items.

This scale was tested on around twenty people in order to detect shortcomings in the structure of the questionnaire and the wording of the questions.

E-reputation measurement scale Rindova et al (2005)

REP1: The fast-food website is improved by the quality of its images

REP2: Internet users evaluate the e-reputation of fast-food restaurants based on the quality of their services

REP3: Fast food's e-reputation is determined by its sales environment

REP4: Customers share their e-experience of fast-food service quality

REP5: The quality of customer relations is an element of customer satisfaction

REP6: The number of subscribers to a fast-food restaurant's Facebook page influences the perception of other customers online.

4. RESULTS

4.1- Analysis of empirical results

Table 1: Breakdown of the sample by gender

	Effectifs	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Accumulated percentage
Female	181	48.4	48.4	48.4
Valid Male	193	51.6	51.6	100.0
Total	374	100.0	100.0	

Source: 2024 survey data

Women represent 48.4% of our workforce, i.e. 181 out of a total of 374. Men represent 51.6%, or 193 people.

Table2: Breakdown of sample by age group

Age	Effectifs	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Accumulated percentage
18 to 25 years	273	63.4	63.4	64.4
25 to 35 years	112	29.9	29.9	94.4
36 to 45 years	17	4.5	4.5	98.9
46 to 55 years	4	1.1	1.1	1.1
> to 55 years	4	1.1	1.1	100.0
Total	374	100.0	100.0	

Source: 2024 survey data

4.2-TESTING AND VALIDATION OF HYPOTHESES

Hypothesis testing of gender moderation on the link between EBAO and E-REPUTATION.

Table3: Model Summary

R	R-sq	MSE	F(HC4)	Df1	Df2	P
0.3405	0.1159	0.8807	9.6522	5.0000	368.0000	0.0000

Source: Data from our survey, 2024

Table4: Result of the moderating effect of gender on the relationship between e-Bao and e-reputation

Variables	Coefficient	T	P	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	3.1640	63.7963	0.0000	3.0664	3.2615
E-wom	0.3231	6.1672	0.0000	0.2201	0.4261
gender	-0.1467	-1.4306	0.1534	-0.3484	0.0549
Interaction between e-wom and gender	-0.0154	-0.1408	0.8881	-0.2303	0.1995

Source: 2024 survey data

According to the results in Table above, the interaction effect is not significant ($d = -0.0154$; $t = -0.1408$; $p = 0.8881 > 0.05$). Thus, these values allow us to affirm that gender has no influence on the relationship between electronic word-of-mouth and e-reputation with regard to the e-reputation of fast-food restaurants in Togo in our research

context. Moreover, the value 0 is within the confidence interval (LLCI = -0.2303 and ULCI = 0.1995). In view of the above results, we can state that gender does not play a moderating role between electronic word of mouth and the e-reputation of fast-food restaurants in Tog

figure2: Graphical representation of the interaction effect between electronic word of mouth and e-reputation. Gender moderation.

Graphical representation of the interaction effect between electronic word of mouth and e-reputation. Gender moderation

The figure above gives us a graphical representation of electronic word of mouth with e-reputation by gender using the results of the Hayes macro process version 3.5. The blue curve represents the curve for men and the green curve represents the curve for women. The results of this graph allow us to state that although gender does not moderate the relationship between the

independent variable e-Bao and the dependent variable e-reputation, the adjustment curves for men and women are both increasing. Parallel and moving in the same direction. This means that women and men are influenced in the same way in our context.

Hypothesis testing of age moderation on the link between E-WOM and E-REPUTATION.

Variables	Coefficient	t	P	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	3.1640	63.7963	0.0000	3.0664	3.2615
E-WOM	0.3231	6.1672	0.0000	0.2201	0.4261
Age	-0.0748	-0.9569	0.3392	-0.2284	0.0789
Interaction between e-wom and Age	-0.0266	-0.2984	0.7655	-0.2019	0.1487

Source: 2024 survey data

According to the results in Table x, the interaction effect is not significant ($d = -0.0266$; $t = -0.2984$; $p = 0.7655 > 0.05$). Thus, these values allow us to affirm that age has no influence on the relationship between electronic word-of-mouth and e-reputation as far as the e-reputation of fast-food restaurants in Togo is concerned in our research context.

Moreover, the value 0 is within the confidence interval ($LLCI = -0.2019$ and $ULCI = 0.1487$). In view of the above results, we can state that age does not play a moderating role between electronic word of mouth and the e-reputation of fast-food restaurants in Togo.

Figure3: Graphical representation of the interaction effect between electronic word of mouth and Age moderation

Graphical representation of the interaction effect between electronic word of mouth and Age moderation

The figure above gives us a graphical representation of electronic word of mouth with e-reputation by age using the result of the Hayes macro process version 3.5. The blue adjustment curve represents the adjustment curve for the age range (18 to 25 years), the green curve

represents the adjustment curve for the age range (25 to 35 years) and the yellow curve represents the adjustment curve for the age range (36 to 45 years), which are the most represented age groups.

The results of this graph allow us to state that although age does not moderate the relationship between the independent variable e-Bao and the dependent variable e-reputation, the age interval adjustment curves are all increasing.

Parallel and evolving in the same direction. This means that age is influenced in our context in the same way.

5. Discussing the results

5.1-Gender moderates the relationship between electronic word of mouth and e-reputation

According to our results, this hypothesis is not validated in our context. This means that according to our research, men and women are influenced in the same way when it comes to electronic word of mouth in relation to the e-reputation of fast-food restaurants in Togo. Our study goes in the opposite direction to several previous studies on purchase intention. According to Darley and Smith (1995), gender also has the capacity to influence the different stages of the consumer's purchasing process (Mitchell & Walsh, 2001) and to moderate their evaluation judgements (Holbrook, 1986). In the absence of conformity of the results of our research in relation to the results of previous work, we feel that it might be of the fact that our sample is made up more of youths who have the same capacity for reflection and analysis. In addition, previous studies have tested purchase intention rather than e-reputation. This uniform reaction is reinforced by our specific area of fast-food in Togo. However, in other areas different from fast-food, we might have a different outcome from our study.

Having different results from others previous studies, as it's the context of our study, contribute effectively to the science

5.2 Age moderates the relationship between electronic word of mouth and e-reputation

According to our results, this hypothesis is not validated in our context. This is contrary to the results of studies conducted by Liao and Fu (2012), who found that online comments are not perceived in the same way depending on the age group to which the individual belongs. More

specifically, compared to young people, older adults appear to be less likely to perceive electronic BAO as credible and to be influenced by it. These results also differ from our own. This may be explained by the context of the study. However, in other areas different from fast-food, we might have a different outcome from our study.

Conclusion

This research has enriched the literature on the role that age and gender can play in exposure to electronic word of mouth on e-reputation and increased the very limited knowledge and results in this area. This work has also demonstrated that customers of all ages in our context act in the same way when exposed to electronic word of mouth on the e-reputation of fast-food restaurants in Togo. From a practical point of view, this study helps marketers, managers and practitioners to take an interest in digital reputation management and its improvement. E-reputation management requires specific management and skills adapted to the characteristics of Web 2.0. It is a real challenge for companies, because it means rethinking the way they listen to consumers. It requires an increasingly participative, less formal and less institutional approach on digital media (blogs, forums, communities, social networks, etc.) than on the brand's or company's institutional website. To achieve this, strategic monitoring tools need to be put in place to identify the opinions expressed online by Internet users (opinion leaders, consumers, employees, etc.) in different forms (comments, rankings, articles, etc.) and via different virtual platforms (communities, networks, blogs, etc.). This makes it possible to measure their number, quality and social influence in order to manage them. Similarly, we need to adopt new consumer behaviour research methodologies such as netnography (Kozinets, 2002) and e-interviews (Maubisson & Abaidi, 2011). Companies should also consider recruiting community managers and using companies specialising in e-reputation management in order to avoid any bad buzz and develop a favourable digital reputation. As far as the limitations of our research are concerned, it can be said that the Togolese context may not be similar to that of other nations; consequently, we cannot afford to generalise our research model. Replications of the study in different countries will strengthen the reliability of the conceptual model and even allow comparisons to be made. In addition, the choice of a single type of service (fast-food) is still rather limiting in terms of results. We suggested the future research to continue with variables such as culture and religion. This could yield other very interesting results.

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